

Supplementary materials for:

The role of muscular fitness on bone mineral content and areal bone mineral density in youth with type 1 diabetes

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Supplemental Table 1. Strengthening the Reporting of OBservational Studies in Epidemiology Statement.

	Item N°	Recommendation	Page N°
Title and abstract	1	(a) Indicate the study's design with a commonly used term in the title or the abstract	1-2
		(b) Provide in the abstract an informative and balanced summary of what was done and what was found	2-3
Introduction			
Background/ rationale	2	Explain the scientific background and rationale for the investigation being reported	5
Objectives	3	State specific objectives, including any prespecified hypotheses	6
Methods			
Study design	4	Present key elements of study design early in the paper	6
Setting	5	Describe the setting, locations, and relevant dates, including periods of recruitment, exposure, follow-up, and data collection	6-7
Participants	6	(a) Give the eligibility criteria, and the sources and methods of selection of participants	7
Variables	7	Clearly define all outcomes, exposures, predictors, potential confounders, and effect modifiers. Give diagnostic criteria, if applicable	8-11
Data sources/ measurement	8	For each variable of interest, give sources of data and details of methods of assessment (measurement). Describe comparability of assessment methods if there is more than one group	8-11
Bias	9	Describe any efforts to address potential sources of bias	6
Study size	10	Explain how the study size was arrived at	6
Quantitative variables	11	Explain how quantitative variables were handled in the analyses. If applicable, describe which groupings were chosen and why	11-12
Statistical methods	12	(a) Describe all statistical methods, including those used to control for confounding	11-13
		(b) Describe any methods used to examine subgroups and interactions	12
		(c) Explain how missing data were addressed	13
		(d) If applicable, describe analytical methods taking account of sampling strategy	Not applicable
		(e) Describe any sensitivity analyses	12
Results			
Participants	13	(a) Report numbers of individuals at each stage of study—eg numbers potentially eligible, examined for eligibility, confirmed eligible, included in the study, completing follow-up, and analysed	Page 13 and Supplemental Fig. 2
Descriptive data	14	(b) Give reasons for non-participation at each stage	14
		(c) Consider use of a flow diagram	Supplemental Fig. 2
		(a) Give characteristics of study participants (eg demographic, clinical, social) and information on exposures and potential confounders	Page 14 and Table 1

		(b) Indicate number of participants with missing data for each variable of interest	14
Outcome data	15	Report numbers of outcome events or summary measures (a) Give unadjusted estimates and, if applicable, confounder-adjusted estimates and their precision (eg, 95% confidence interval). Make clear which confounders were adjusted for and why they were included	Table 1 Supplemental Fig. 1
Main results	16	(b) Report category boundaries when continuous variables were categorized (c) If relevant, consider translating estimates of relative risk into absolute risk for a meaningful time period	15 Not applicable Supplemental Table 2; Supplemental Table 4; Supplemental Table 5; Supplemental figure 4
Other analyses	17	Report other analyses done—eg analyses of subgroups and interactions, and sensitivity analyses	
Discussion			
Key results	18	Summarise key results with reference to study objectives	16
Limitations	19	Discuss limitations of the study, taking into account sources of potential bias or imprecision. Discuss both direction and magnitude of any potential bias	18-19
Interpretation	20	Give a cautious overall interpretation of results considering objectives, limitations, multiplicity of analyses, results from similar studies, and other relevant evidence	17
Generalisability	21	Discuss the generalisability (external validity) of the study results	19
Other information			
Funding	22	Give the source of funding and the role of the funders for the present study and, if applicable, for the original study on which the present article is based	20

Supplemental Table 2. Differences between those who left the study and those who continued the 1st and 2nd year follow-up.

Variables	Lost to follow-up	Followed 1 st and 2 nd year	<i>p</i> -value
Age (years)	15 (3) ^b	13 (5) ^b	0.200
Diabetes Duration (years)	4 (4) ^b	3 (5) ^b	0.258
Anthropometric			
Body height (m)	1.6 (0.2) ^b	1.5 (0.1) ^b	0.271
Body weight (kg)	54.80 ± 19.25 ^a	50.33 ± 16.04 ^a	0.328
Body mass index (kg/m ²)	20.19 (6.23) ^b	19.30 (4.18) ^b	0.442
Body mass index (z-score)	0.6 ± 1.1 ^a	0.6 ± 0.9 ^a	0.877
Peak height velocity (score)	-0.3 ± 2.1 ^a	-0.5 ± 1.8 ^a	0.683
Diabetes-related assessment			
HbA1c (%)	7.5 ± 0.7 ^a	7.3 ± 0.8 ^a	0.282
Daily insulin dose (U/kg)	0.68 (0.30) ^b	0.71 (0.31) ^b	0.904
Physical activity			
Total PA (min)	307 ± 77 ^a	341 ± 81 ^a	0.095
Muscle Strength			
Handgrip strength (z-score)	-1.0 (0.9) ^b	-0.4 (0.8) ^b	0.022
Handgrip strength (kg)	20.6 (14.0) ^b	20.5 (10.1) ^b	0.558
Total RM (score)	0.3 (2.6) ^b	-0.7 (4.3) ^b	0.264
Total power (score)	0.2 (2.5) ^b	-0.8 (4.5) ^b	0.377
Bone health parameters			
<i>Bone mineral content (BMC)</i>			
TBLH (z-score)	0.9 ± 1.2 ^a	1.1 ± 1.1 ^a	0.496
TBLH (g)	1598.47 ± 632.83 ^a	1476.53 ± 522.98 ^a	0.416
Arms (g)	243.23 ± 97.01 ^a	228.56 ± 83.02 ^a	0.525
Legs (g)	779.02 ± 304.82 ^a	711.81 ± 241.77 ^a	0.349
Pelvis (g)	250.43 (177.24) ^b	234.96 (155.99) ^b	0.607
Spine (g)	139.11 (87.97) ^b	120.83 (79.06) ^b	0.538
<i>Bone mineral density (BMD)</i>			
TBLH (z-score)	0.5 (2.0) ^b	0.9 (1.4) ^b	0.362
TBLH (g/cm ²)	0.927 ± 0.182 ^a	0.900 ± 0.166 ^a	0.546
Arms (g/cm ²)	0.711 ± 0.142 ^a	0.701 ± 0.127 ^a	0.769
Legs (g/cm ²)	1.093 ± 0.213 ^a	1.062 ± 0.196 ^a	0.542
Pelvis (g/cm ²)	0.962 (0.324) ^b	0.897 (0.311) ^b	0.418
Spine (g/cm ²)	0.925 (0.264) ^b	0.851 (0.314) ^b	0.466

Note: **HbA1c**, glycosylated hemoglobin; **PA**, physical activity; **RM**, maximum repetition; **TBLH**, total body less head; **p-value**, statistical significance.

^a Normal variables: mean ± standard deviation [SD].

^b Non-normal variables: median (interquartile range [IQR]).

'*p*': *p*-value in Mann-Whitney *U* test or *t* test for differences between those who left the study and those who continued the 1st and 2nd year follow-up.

Bold (*p* < 0.05) implies difference in means.

Supplemental Figure 1. Directed acyclic graph (DAG).

Panel A represents the DAG for the causal structure of the relationship between muscle fitness (exposure, green square with a “▶”) and bone health (outcome, blue square with an “I”). Pink squares indicate variables reported in the literature to be related to both exposure and outcome (Sex, Age, Peak height velocity, Disease duration, Body mass index, Calcium, Physical activity, Glycosylated hemoglobin, Insulin, Interpersonal difference). Blue squares (Insulin and Vitamin D) indicate relationships only with the outcome according to the literature. Green arrows indicate “causal” trajectories, and pink arrows indicate biased trajectories.

Panel B shows the Directed Acyclic Graph (DAG) after adjusting for the minimum sufficient set of confounders, including PHV, disease duration, BMI, HbA1c, insulin, calcium intake, and physical activity (gray squares). The bias paths (pink arrows) were closed by controlling these variables according to the literature, turning them into black arrows. Only the causal pathways (green arrows) remain open, including the direct and indirect pathways from muscle fitness to bone health. The blue square (vitamin D), related only to the outcome in the literature, remains unchanged due to lack of data.

A)

B)

Supplemental Figure 2. Flow chart.

Supplemental Table 3. Results of the 2-year longitudinal multiple linear mixed model analysis for the associations of handgrip strength standardized z-score based on reference percentiles, with age-, sex- and race-specific bone mineral content (BMC) z-score (A) or bone mineral density [BMD] z-score (B).

<i>BMC, total body less head (z – value)</i>					
<i>Fixed effects</i>	<i>B</i>	<i>SE</i>	<i>95% CI</i>		<i>p-value</i>
			<i>Lower</i>	<i>Upper</i>	
Handgrip strength (z-score)	0.194	0.054	0.088	0.300	≤0.001
Time of assessment	-0.045	0.040	-0.125	0.033	0.260
Diabetes duration	0.025	0.034	-0.042	0.092	0.466
HbA1c	-0.057	0.028	-0.112	-0.002	0.038
Body mass index (z-score)	0.148	0.058	0.034	0.262	0.010
Daily insulin dose	0.130	0.144	-0.151	0.412	0.365
<i>Random effects</i>					
	<i>σ</i>	<i>σ</i> ²			
Participants	1.044	1.021			
<i>BMD, total body less head (z – value)</i>					
<i>Fixed effects</i>	<i>B</i>	<i>SE</i>	<i>95% CI</i>		<i>p-value</i>
			<i>Lower</i>	<i>Upper</i>	
Handgrip strength (z-score)	0.350	0.071	0.210	0.490	≤0.001
Time of assessment	-0.008	0.042	-0.091	0.074	0.836
Diabetes duration	0.018	0.029	-0.038	0.075	0.530
HbA1c	-0.028	0.039	-0.105	0.047	0.459
Body mass index (z – score)	0.475	0.070	0.336	0.614	≤0.001
Daily insulin dose	-0.093	0.190	-0.466	0.279	0.623
<i>Random effects</i>					
	<i>σ</i>	<i>σ</i> ²			
Participants	0.710	0.843			

Note: **B**, unstandardized beta coefficient; **BMC**, body mineral content; **BMD**, body mineral density; **CI**, confidence interval; **HbA1c**, glycosylated hemoglobin; **p-value**, statistical significance; **SE**, standard error; **σ**, standard deviation; **σ**², variance.

A total of 183 observations were observed in the models. The BMC model had a coefficient of determination (R_c^2) of 0.96 with an intraclass correlation coefficient (ICC) of 0.96, while the BMD model had a R_c^2 of 0.89 and an ICC of 0.89.

Bold ($p < 0.05$) implies difference in means.

Supplemental Figure 3. Differences between having a percentile above 20 and having a percentile below 20 within handgrip strength reference values in bone mineral content z-scores (A) or bone mineral density z-score (B).

Supplemental Table 4. Interaction effects of time and maturation on the association between different parameters of muscle fitness and bone mineral content (BMC) in different body sections in a 2-year longitudinal linear mixed model analysis.

		<i>Total body less head</i>					
		Handgrip strength		RM		Power strength	
		<i>B</i>	<i>p</i> -value	<i>B</i>	<i>p</i> -value	<i>B</i>	<i>p</i> -value
<i>Time</i>							
	Baseline (Ref.)	22.388		21.621		28.797	
	Follow-up 1	-4.119	0.004	-1.405	0.738	-2.416	0.541
	Follow-up 2	-5.249	0.002	-3.265	0.508	-2.728	0.541
<i>Maturation</i>							
	Pre-puberal (Ref.)	39.393		15.068		27.870	
	Peri-puberal	-12.235	0.048	7.741	0.455	6.400	0.519
	Post-puberal	-18.428	0.006	5.007	0.669	0.488	0.967
		<i>Arms</i>					
		Handgrip strength		RM		Power strength	
		<i>B</i>	<i>p</i> -value	<i>B</i>	<i>p</i> -value	<i>B</i>	<i>p</i> -value
<i>Time</i>							
	Baseline (Ref.)	4.376		3.800		4.645	
	Follow-up 1	-0.432	0.142	-1.103	0.209	-0.919	0.275
	Follow-up 2	-0.317	0.350	-0.424	0.678	-0.258	0.785
<i>Maturation</i>							
	Pre-puberal (Ref.)	6.923		2.911		4.122	
	Peri-puberal	-1.724	0.140	0.486	0.802	0.767	0.678
	Post-puberal	-1.985	0.085	0.227	0.916	0.696	0.752
		<i>Legs</i>					
		Handgrip strength		RM		Power strength	
		<i>B</i>	<i>p</i> -value	<i>B</i>	<i>p</i> -value	<i>B</i>	<i>p</i> -value
<i>Time</i>							
	Baseline (Ref.)	11.708		10.224		14.533	
	Follow-up 1	-2.671	≤0.001	-0.647	0.774	-1.054	0.612
	Follow-up 2	-4.038	≤0.001	-1.772	0.503	-1.422	0.545
<i>Maturation</i>							
	Pre-puberal (Ref.)	21.878		8.353		15.016	
	Peri-puberal	-10.263	≤0.001	0.761	0.882	0.317	0.947
	Post-puberal	-11.912	≤0.001	0.508	0.930	-1.822	0.755
		<i>Pelvis</i>					
		Handgrip strength		RM		Power strength	
		<i>B</i>	<i>p</i> -value	<i>B</i>	<i>p</i> -value	<i>B</i>	<i>p</i> -value
<i>Time</i>							
	Baseline (Ref.)	4.321		5.234		6.348	
	Follow-up 1	-0.768	0.044	0.513	0.610	0.204	0.826
	Follow-up 2	-0.862	0.049	0.267	0.819	0.513	0.624
<i>Maturation</i>							
	Pre-puberal (Ref.)	7.098		4.443		5.917	
	Peri-puberal	-1.083	0.463	0.542	0.814	1.006	0.645
	Post-puberal	-2.916	0.043	2.256	0.373	2.071	0.420
		<i>Spine</i>					
		Handgrip strength		RM		Power strength	
		<i>B</i>	<i>p</i> -value	<i>B</i>	<i>p</i> -value	<i>B</i>	<i>p</i> -value
<i>Time</i>							

Baseline (Ref.)	0.876		1.216		1.480	
Follow-up 1	-0.193	0.240	-0.153	0.749	-0.119	0.793
Follow-up 2	0.125	0.518	0.178	0.751	0.342	0.504
<i>Maturation</i>						
Pre-puberal (Ref.)	2.147		0.955		2.007	
Peri-puberal	-0.536	0.416	0.826	0.411	0.377	0.694
Post-puberal	-1.000	0.134	-0.186	0.870	-0.722	0.536

Note: **B**, unstandardized beta coefficient; **RM**, maximum repetition; **p-value**, statistical significance; **Ref.**, reference group.

Bold ($p < 0.05$) implies difference in means.

Supplemental Table 5. Interaction effects of time and maturation on the association between different parameters of muscle fitness and bone mineral content (BMC) in different body sections in a 2-year longitudinal linear mixed model analysis.

		<i>Total body less head</i>					
		Handgrip strength		RM		Power strength	
		<i>B</i>	<i>p</i> -value	<i>B</i>	<i>p</i> -value	<i>B</i>	<i>p</i> -value
<i>Time</i>							
	Baseline (Ref.)	0.005		0.008		0.009	
	Follow-up 1	-0.000	0.116	-0.000	0.699	-0.001	0.457
	Follow-up 2	-0.001	0.982	-0.000	0.670	-0.000	0.822
<i>Maturation</i>							
	Pre-puberal (Ref.)	0.009		0.006		0.008	
	Peri-puberal	-0.002	0.295	0.001	0.671	0.002	0.524
	Post-puberal	-0.003	0.119	0.002	0.529	0.002	0.540
		<i>Arms</i>					
		Handgrip strength		RM		Power strength	
		<i>B</i>	<i>p</i> -value	<i>B</i>	<i>p</i> -value	<i>B</i>	<i>p</i> -value
<i>Time</i>							
	Baseline (ref)	0.002		0.007		0.006	
	Follow-up 1	0.000	0.510	-0.002	0.284	-0.002	0.236
	Follow-up 2	0.000	0.695	-0.000	0.899	0.000	0.914
<i>Maturation</i>							
	Pre-puberal (ref)	0.003		0.004		0.004	
	Peri-puberal	0.001	0.671	0.003	0.324	0.005	0.186
	Post-puberal	0.000	0.721	0.000	0.824	0.001	0.704
		<i>Legs</i>					
		Handgrip strength		RM		Power strength	
		<i>B</i>	<i>p</i> -value	<i>B</i>	<i>p</i> -value	<i>B</i>	<i>p</i> -value
<i>Time</i>							
	Baseline (Ref.)	0.009		0.009		0.011	
	Follow-up 1	-0.001	0.048	0.001	0.566	0.000	0.730
	Follow-up 2	-0.001	0.047	0.001	0.655	0.001	0.511
<i>Maturation</i>							
	Pre-puberal (Ref.)	0.016		0.007		0.010	
	Peri-puberal	-0.007	0.015	-0.001	0.716	-0.000	0.925
	Post-puberal	-0.009	0.002	0.003	0.393	0.004	0.331
		<i>Pelvis</i>					
		Handgrip strength		RM		Power strength	
		<i>B</i>	<i>p</i> -value	<i>B</i>	<i>p</i> -value	<i>B</i>	<i>p</i> -value
<i>Time</i>							
	Baseline (Ref.)	0.008		0.010		0.013	
	Follow-up 1	-0.002	0.011	-0.000	0.947	-0.000	0.657
	Follow-up 2	-0.002	0.009	-0.000	0.929	0.000	0.827
<i>Maturation</i>							
	Pre-puberal (Ref.)	0.010		0.005		0.008	
	Peri-puberal	-0.001	0.745	0.005	0.251	0.006	0.015
	Post-puberal	-0.004	0.216	0.008	0.085	0.008	0.074
		<i>Spine</i>					
		Handgrip strength		RM		Power strength	
		<i>B</i>	<i>p</i> -value	<i>B</i>	<i>p</i> -value	<i>B</i>	<i>p</i> -value
<i>Time</i>							

Baseline (Ref.)	0.003		0.005		0.006	
Follow-up 1	-0.000	0.404	-0.000	0.815	-0.000	0.678
Follow-up 2	0.000	0.728	0.001	0.381	0.001	0.372
<i>Maturation</i>						
Pre-puberal (Ref.)	0.004		0.002		0.007	
Peri-puberal	0.001	0.541	0.003	0.383	0.001	0.600
Post-puberal	0.000	0.870	0.004	0.347	0.001	0.737

Note: **B**, unstandardized beta coefficient; **RM**, maximum repetition; **p-value**, statistical significance; **Ref.**, reference group.

Bold ($p < 0.05$) implies difference in means.

Supplemental figure 4. Interaction effects of time on the associations of handgrip strength standardized z-score based on reference percentiles, with age-, sex- and race-specific bone mineral content (BMC) z-score (A) or bone mineral density [BMD] z-score (B).

A)

B)

